

MONDAY April 3

BLOCK I

9:30–11:15

**Six periods in the history
of Czech school atlases**

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The paper introduces a short history of Czech School atlases in periods.

The first period (until the middle of the 18th century) was the use of commonly available German and Austrian maps, globes and atlases designed specifically for schools. After 1850, the original Czech cartographic production of school atlases appeared thanks to the awakening of national consciousness.

The second period (around 1850) is the Merklas atlases. Václav Merklas (1809–1866) was mainly a copper engraver, cartography was not his main profession. Between 1842 and 1858, in cooperation with the revival society *Matice česká*, he published five atlases by translation of German and Austrian atlases. Although the atlases were quickly distributed to schools, the interest of the schools soon failed due to the unreliability of Merklas himself.

The third period (1850–1918) is defined by Kozenn's atlases. Blasius Kozenn (1821–1871) taught in Olomouc, where he met the bookseller Eduard Hölzel, who persuaded him to compile a school atlas, which Austrian schools were still lacking. Hölzel founded a bookshop in Olomouc in 1848, then moved it to Vienna, where it is still Verlag Ed. Hölzel. In 1861, he published Kozenn's first school atlas which became a bestseller in Austrian schools and was translated into Polish, Croatian, Czech and Italian. Atlases for Austrian schools are still published under the title *Kozenn-Schulatlas*.

In the fourth period (1918–1948), after the establishment of independent Czechoslovakia, the *School Geographical Atlas* was compiled by J. Brunclík and F. Machát, and later reworked by Šalamon and Kuchař. It was one of the best produced in the Czech lands. Geographical maps prevailed, thematic maps were more frequent, they were prepared for the whole world and did not have an index. After the Second World War, the atlas was out of date, but from the mid-1950s there was a rapid increase in the number of published works – it was divided into national and world and an index was introduced.

The fifth period (1948–1989) is characterized by the world atlases of the Unified System of School Cartographic Aids (USSCA), a unified concept for the systematization and stabilization of teaching. It was built on cartographic and pedagogic research which included an analysis of teaching aids for geography, history and national history. The aim was to maintain uniformity in all cartographic aids used in education in terms of scales, legends, cartographic means of expression, etc.

In the last, current period (atlases after 1989), the publishing of atlases according to the USSCA was continued by the monopoly publisher Kartografie Praha. Later it was reworked into the School Atlas of the World for secondary schools and the Pupils' Atlas for primary schools. In the mid-1990s, Kartografie Praha began publishing atlases based on the primary school geography curriculum for individual grades. Other publishers of school atlases gradually became TERRA, SHOCart and Geodézie ČS.

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NOTES

A large area of dotted lines for taking notes, consisting of a grid of small dots.